

Research article

Physicomechanical performance of chitosan-coated mycelium composites from birch sanding dust and wheat straw

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ABSTRACT

Industrial and agricultural by-products, birch sanding dust (BSD) and wheat straw (WS), were valorized as substrates for the fabrication of mycelium-based composites (MBCs) using the living mycelium of the basidiomycete *Trametes versicolor*. The composites were functionalized with a chitosan surface coating in 2- and 4-layer configurations. Microscopy, mechanical properties (compressive and flexural strength), water absorption, hygroscopic behavior, and surface wettability were evaluated. BSD-based composites outperformed WS-based blends in both mechanical properties, exhibiting flexural strength 1.3 – 1.7 × higher and compressive strength 2.1 – 3.4 × higher, depending on the layer configuration. Compressive strength was more strongly affected by density than by chitosan coating. Chitosan functionalization reduced water absorption in WS-based composites by up to 30%. WS-based composites exhibited greater hygroscopic adsorption than BSD-based blends. Chitosan coating maintained moisture adsorption values close to 20% at 90% RH, whereas at 95% RH, moisture uptake increased to 20–46%. For BSD-based specimens, chitosan-coated surfaces reached contact angles below 60° within 30 s, while WS-based composites fell below 40°, indicating a more hydrophilic character of the WS substrate. The novelty of this work lies in demonstrating a practical, scalable coating approach to modestly enhance the durability and moisture resistance of MBCs, thereby supporting their wider application in eco-product design.

1. Introduction

The environmental cost of synthetic materials continues to rise, driven by the global demand for packaging, construction, and insulation products. These conventional materials, particularly expanded polystyrene (EPS), polyurethane foams, and other petrochemical-based composites, are valued for their performance but come with serious trade-offs [1,2]. Their production is energy-intensive, they are difficult to recycle, and they often persist for decades in landfills [3]. In many cases, disposal through incineration contributes to greenhouse gas emissions and toxic byproducts [4,5]. As global regulations tighten and sustainability targets grow more urgent, there is a clear need to identify alternative materials that align with circular economy principles [6].

At the same time, agricultural and wood-processing industries generate large volumes of lignocellulosic by-products that are frequently underutilized or treated as waste. Valorizing these residues as feedstocks for alternative bio-based materials offers a promising pathway to reduce environmental impacts while creating added value from industrial side

streams [7,8]. One such alternative is found in mycelium-based composites (MBCs), biomaterials produced by growing fungal mycelium on organic substrates [9,10]. During growth, the fungal hyphae colonize and bind together lignocellulosic particles such as straw, sawdust, hemp shives, etc., forming a cohesive, foam-like composite [11]. MBCs are fully biodegradable, sourced from renewable feedstocks, and can be shaped using low-energy processes. Their production not only reduces reliance on synthetic binders but also transforms biomass waste into functional materials, offering a dual environmental benefit [12].

Rising atmospheric CO₂ concentrations have significant consequences for global climate stability and ecosystem functioning. Mitigating these impacts requires a reduction in the carbon footprint of industrial products through the development of renewable, low-impact material alternatives. In this context, MBCs have attracted increasing attention as sustainable biomaterials derived from natural resources. These materials can contribute to a carbon-neutral future, as the plant-based substrates used for fungal growth originate from atmospheric CO₂ sequestered through photosynthesis and subsequently converted into

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organic carbon incorporated into fungal biomass.

However, several challenges limit the real-world usability of MBCs, particularly in moisture-sensitive or mechanically demanding applications. A primary concern is water absorption. The porous and hydrophilic structure of mycelium composites leads to rapid uptake of moisture, resulting in dimensional instability, loss of mechanical strength, and vulnerability to microbial contamination [13,14]. These factors significantly restrict their use in insulation, packaging, or interior design, where humidity or incidental water exposure may occur. In addition, mechanical properties such as compressive and bending strength are often below those of standard synthetic foams, requiring enhancement for broader application [15].

To address these limitations, researchers have explored the use of surface coatings and post-processing treatments [16,17]. Natural waxes and oils can provide modest water resistance, while some bio-based polymers offer structural reinforcement [18,19]. However, many existing treatments either compromise the compostability of the final product, rely on synthetic additives, or are insufficiently effective over time. The ideal coating would be bio-based, biodegradable, and functionally compatible with the mycelium substrate.

Chitosan has emerged as a promising candidate. This polysaccharide, derived primarily from crustacean shells or fungal biomass, is well known for its film-forming, antimicrobial, and water-resistant properties [20–22]. It has been widely studied in food packaging, biomedical applications, and paper coatings, where it serves as a biodegradable barrier against moisture and microbes [23,24]. Beyond these applications, fungal-based chitosan nanoparticles have recently attracted attention as sustainable soil amendments [25] and the agents for removing toxic dyes from water [26]. Importantly, its chemical similarity to fungal cell walls and its ability to adhere to porous natural materials make it particularly well-suited for integration with MBCs [20,27].

In this study, we focus on applying chitosan as a surface coating for MBCs cultivated with basidiomycete *Trametes versicolor* on a variety of lignocellulosic substrates. By applying two and four layers of chitosan solution and measuring their effects, we assess the impact of coating on mechanical performance, water absorption, and surface wettability, including contact angle analysis. The contribution of this work lies in (i) the application of a simple and scalable multi-layer chitosan coating approach, and (ii) the comparative evaluation of its effects across different lignocellulosic substrate systems, wheat straw (WS) and birch sanding dust (BSD), highlighting substrate-dependent performance.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Lignocellulosic substrates

The lignocellulosic substrates used for the fabrication of mycelium-based composites (MBCs) were sourced from local industries. The primary substrates, WS and BSD, were obtained from Latgale Agricultural Science Center Ltd. (Vilani, Latvia) and the plywood producer Latvijas Finieris JSC (Riga, Latvia), respectively. Hemp shives (HS), used as a co-substrate, were purchased from a local building supply store, while birch sawdust (BS) was provided by the wood-processing company Osukalns Ltd. (Jekabpils, Latvia). Wheat bran (WB), used as an additive, was obtained from a commercial supplier.

Particle size distribution of WS, BSD, and the co-substrates HS and BS was determined using an AS200 analytical sieve shaker (Retsch GmbH, Haan, Germany) equipped with vertically arranged sieves of 10, 7, 5, and 3 mm. The material retained on each sieve was weighed, and the corresponding fraction was expressed as a percentage of the total sample mass (Table 1).

The primary substrates, WS and BSD, were prepared in four different combinations by incorporating hemp shives (HS) or birch sawdust (BS) as co-substrates and wheat bran (WB) as an additive to obtain various composite blends (Table 2).

Table 1

The particle size and weight percentage of each fraction in raw materials of the primary substrates wheat straw (WS), birch sanding dust (BSD), and co-substrates hemp shives (HS), and birch sawdust (BS).

Fraction size (mm)	WS (wt%)	BSD (wt%)	HS (wt%)	BS (wt%)
≥ 10	0	0	8	5
7	0	0	10	1
5	1	0	28	4
3	45	0	37	21
< 3	54	100	17	69

Table 2

Composition of MBC blends with primary substrates birch sanding dust (BSD) and wheat straw (WS), co-substrates hemp shives (HS) and birch sawdust (BS), and wheat bran (WB) as an additive.

MBC Blend	Ingredient (%)				
	BSD	WS	HS	BS	WB
BSD1	100	-	-	-	8
BSD2	50	-	50	-	8
BSD3	50	-	-	50	8
BSD4	100	-	-	-	-
WS1	-	100	-	-	8
WS2	-	50	50	-	8
WS3	-	50	-	50	8
WS4	-	100	-	-	-

2.2. Chemicals

Chitosan of medium molecular weight (430 kDa) and > 90% deacetylation, sourced from crustaceans, was supplied by Jiangsu Aoxin Biotechnology Co., Ltd. (Lianyungang, China). Citric acid, glucose, peptone, yeast extract, NaH₂PO₄, K₂HPO₄, MgSO₄ and NH₄OH were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany).

2.3. Fungal inoculum

The basidiomycete strain *Trametes versicolor* CTB 863 A was initially cultured on malt extract agar (MEA) medium containing 5% malt extract and 3% agar for 14 days at 22 ± 2 °C and 70 ± 5% relative humidity (RH) to prepare the inoculum for liquid cultivation. Liquid cultivation was employed to produce mycelial pellets for subsequent substrate inoculation in the fabrication of MBCs. For this purpose, 250 mL Erlenmeyer flasks were filled with 100 mL of nutrient medium containing (g/L distilled water): glucose, 15.0; peptone, 3.0; yeast extract, 3.0; NaH₂PO₄, 0.8; K₂HPO₄, 0.4; MgSO₄, 0.5 (pH 6.0). After sterilization, each flask was inoculated with a 1 cm² mycelial disc and incubated for 14 days in a rotary shaker incubator (Infors, Switzerland). At the end of the incubation period, the fungal biomass concentration reached 0.66 g·100 mL⁻¹.

2.4. Development of MBCs

A schematic overview of the biofabrication process of MBCs is presented in Fig. 1. Substrates were placed in 4 L filter patch bags and sterilized by autoclaving at 135 °C for 30 min. After cooling, the substrates were aseptically inoculated with a homogenized liquid culture of *T. versicolor* at a 1:1 (v/w) ratio, referring to the ratio of culture volume to primary substrate dry weight. The inoculated bags were incubated at 22 ± 2 °C and 70 ± 5% RH in the dark for 14 days. Following the initial colonization phase, the substrate–mycelium mixture was aseptically transferred into molds (200 × 200 × 40 mm) for a secondary growth stage. The molds were incubated under the same conditions for an additional 7 days. After full development, the MBC panels were removed from the molds, weighed, and oven-dried at 70 °C for 24 h to inactivate

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the biofabrication of chitosan-functionalized MBCs.

fungal growth and calculate the moisture content. The dried composite plates were then cut into specimens of $30 \times 30 \times 30$ mm and $170 \times 30 \times 30$ mm for subsequent physicochemical analyses.

2.5. Surface functionalization with chitosan coating

A 4% (w/w) chitosan solution in 8% (w/w) citric acid was prepared for the surface functionalization of MBC specimens. 40 g of chitosan was dissolved in 1 L of 8% citric acid solution under continuous mechanical stirring at 70 °C until complete dissolution was achieved. The solution was allowed to rest for 12 – 24 h before use to ensure full homogenization and to minimize the risk of depolymerization. The prepared chitosan solution in citric acid had a pH of 2.7 and a dynamic viscosity of 425 mPa·s, with viscosity measured using the ViscoQC 300 (Anton Paar GmbH, Austria) and pH determined using the Orion Star A211 (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA). Before coating, specimens were weighed to determine their initial mass. Chitosan was applied using a spray coating system consisting of a paint spray gun 150129XSTN (Stanley, USA) equipped with a 0.5 mm nozzle, operated at a pressure of 6 bar. The solution was sprayed from a constant distance of 15 cm, with each layer deposited by a controlled sweeping motion lasting 2 s from left to right, followed by 2 s from right to left (total 4 s per layer), ensuring uniform coverage. This procedure was applied to all six faces of the specimens, with either two or four successive layers formed by repeating the same deposition cycle. Each additional layer was deposited only after the previous one had dried, with a minimum drying interval of 2 h between applications. These configurations were chosen to evaluate the incremental effect of coating buildup on composite performance. After drying of the final coating layer, the specimens were placed on a mesh support inside a sealed 65 L container, with a vessel containing 250 mL of 25% aqueous ammonia solution positioned approximately 15 cm below the samples. The container was tightly closed with a hermetic lid to allow ammonia vapor, generated from the solution, to accumulate and interact with the specimens, which were exposed under these conditions for 12 h at ambient temperature to enhance surface hydrophobicity. Ammonia vapor reacts with residual citric acid present in the chitosan film, forming ammonium salts and neutralizing the acid groups. As a result, the acidic environment within the coating is reduced, which decreases the solubility of chitosan upon subsequent contact with water. Finally, the coated specimens were reweighed, and coating uptake was calculated based on the exposed surface area and expressed as coating weight per unit area ($\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$).

2.6. Microscopic analyses

The microstructure of the MBCs was examined using a Leica S9i digital stereo microscope equipped with a 10 MP integrated camera (Leica Microsystems, Wetzlar, Germany). Cross-sections of untreated specimens ($30 \times 30 \times 30$ mm) and chitosan-coated surfaces were examined at $50 \times$ magnification. Images were captured and analyzed using Leica LAS V 4.12.0 software and stored in a digital database.

2.7. Evaluation of mechanical properties

2.7.1. Density

The specimens were conditioned at 20 ± 2 °C and $65 \pm 5\%$ RH until equilibrium moisture was achieved. Subsequently, they were weighed, and dimensions (length, width, and thickness) were measured using a digital caliper. The specimen volume was calculated using Eq. 1, and the density was determined using Eq. 2:

$$V = \frac{l \times w \times h}{1000} \quad (1)$$

where V is the volume (cm^{-3}), and l , w , and h are the length, width, and height (mm), respectively.

$$\rho = \frac{m}{V} \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the density ($\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$), m is the mass (g), and V is the volume (cm^{-3}).

2.7.2. Compression strength

Compression tests were performed on five replicate specimens with dimensions of $30 \times 30 \times 30$ mm using a universal testing machine (Zwick/Roell Z010, Germany). The procedure followed a modified version of ISO 844:2007 and was conducted under controlled room conditions (23 °C, 50% RH). Mechanical load was applied up to 10% relative deformation at a loading rate of 10% strain $\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, with a pre-load of 2 N. Stress–strain curves were recorded in real time using the Zwick/Roell testing software. The compressive modulus of elasticity (E) was determined as the slope of the linear elastic region of the stress–strain curve. Compressive strength (σ_{10}) and elastic modulus values were calculated automatically by the software. To assess mechanical performance independent of density effects, specific compressive strength and specific modulus were calculated as the ratios of compressive strength and modulus to composite density ($\text{MPa}\cdot\text{cm}^3\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), respectively.

2.7.3. Flexural strength

Flexural properties were evaluated using five replicate specimens with dimensions of 170 × 30 × 30 mm. Testing was performed on a universal testing machine (Zwick/Roell Z010, ZwickRoell, Ulm, Germany) following the ISO 1209–2:2007 standard under controlled laboratory conditions (23 °C, 50% RH). A three-point bending configuration was applied with a support span of 150 mm. The load was applied at a crosshead speed of 10 mm·min⁻¹ with a pre-load of 1 N. Maximum flexural strength (σ_{FM}) and flexural modulus of elasticity (E_f) were determined automatically by the testing software. Specific flexural strength and specific modulus were calculated as the ratios of maximum flexural strength and modulus to composite density, respectively.

2.8. Water absorption

Water absorption was determined according to ASTM D1037:2012. Three conditioned specimens (30 × 30 × 30 mm) from each MBC blend were immersed in distilled water for 2 h and 24 h. Water absorption was calculated from the increase in specimen mass after immersion and expressed as a percentage of the initial conditioned weight.

2.9. Hygroscopic sorption

Hygroscopic sorption behavior was evaluated in accordance with ASTM C1498–01:2017. Three specimens (30 × 30 × 30 mm) from each MBC blend were oven-dried at 50 °C to constant mass. The dried specimens were then placed in a climate chamber (Binder MKF 240, BINDER GmbH, Tuttlingen, Germany) maintained at 23 °C and exposed to a series of controlled environments with stepwise increasing RH from 50% to 95%. Specimens were periodically weighed until equilibrium mass was reached at each RH level. The equilibrium moisture content (%) was calculated from the difference between the equilibrium mass at each condition and the oven-dry mass, according to Eq. 3:

$$u (\%) = \frac{m - m_0}{m_0} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

where u is equilibrium moisture content (%); m is the mean mass of the specimens at equilibrium (g); m_0 is the mean mass of the dry specimens (g).

2.10. Contact angle measurements

Static water contact angle measurements were performed on MBC specimens (30 × 30 × 30 mm) using an OCA20 goniometer (Data-Physics Instruments, Filderstadt, Germany) equipped with a video camera and analysis software for droplet contour evaluation. The sessile drop method was applied using distilled water as the probe liquid. Droplets with a volume of 10 μ L were deposited on the specimen surface, and contact angle data were recorded over 60 s at 1 s intervals. Reported values represent the arithmetic mean of three independent measurements for each sample. No additional surface preparation was performed before measurements to preserve the native surface characteristics of the material. For each specimen, multiple measurement locations were selected where the surface appeared locally uniform and relatively flat within the camera's field of view, enabling reliable droplet profile analysis despite the inherent roughness and porosity of the specimens.

2.11. Statistical analysis

All statistical analyses and visualizations were conducted in R (version 4.4.2) using RStudio. Assumptions of normality and homogeneity of variance were assessed using Q–Q plots, the Shapiro–Wilk test, and Levene's test. Moisture sorption (hygroscopicity) and water absorption data were analyzed using linear mixed-effects models (LMMs).

Relative humidity, time, substrate type, and number of chitosan layers were included as fixed effects (as applicable to each response variable), while sample ID was included as a random intercept to account for repeated measurements within specimens. Alternative model structures, including different combinations of fixed effects and interaction terms, were compared, and the optimal model was selected based on Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC). Mechanical properties were analyzed using generalized linear models (GLMs), as no repeated measurements were obtained per sample. Substrate type and number of chitosan layers were included as fixed effects. Appropriate error distributions and link functions were selected based on data characteristics, and model assumptions were evaluated using residual diagnostics. Post hoc pairwise comparisons were performed using estimated marginal means (EMMs). Relationships between mechanical variables were assessed using Spearman's rank correlation. Statistical significance was defined at $\alpha = 0.05$.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Micromorphology

BSD-based composites exhibited a dense and compact microstructure, characterized by small voids and a well-developed mycelial network that surrounded individual wood cell particles and resulted in a relatively homogeneous structure across blends BSD1–BSD4 (Fig. 2). In contrast, WS-containing composites displayed a looser and more porous morphology, which indicated more limited fungal colonization within the substrate. Blends WS1–WS4 showed a heterogeneous particle distribution with larger void spaces that contained only sparse mycelial growth.

The final moisture content of the composites varied depending on the formulation, ranging from 62 to 65% for BSD composites and 63–66% for WS composites, which is sufficient to support fungal growth. Therefore, the observed differences in mycelial distribution are likely attributable to morphological, chemical, and structural variations between birch wood and wheat straw. Wheat straw lignin is characterized by a higher content of *p*-hydroxyphenyl units, a more amorphous and branched structure, and a shorter polymer chain length compared to wood lignin. In addition, wheat straw contains *p*-coumaric acid, ferulic acid, and the flavone tricetin, compounds known to inhibit fungal growth and potentially hinder mycelial colonization [28–30]. Furthermore, the influence of extractives on hyphal development cannot be excluded, as wheat straw contains a heterogeneous mixture of resin acids, sterol esters, waxes, triglycerides, fatty acids, sterols, fatty alcohols, and various phenolic compounds [31].

3.2. Surface functionalization with chitosan

Representative micrographs of the chitosan coating are shown in Fig. 3. The smaller particle size of BSD (Table 1) contributed to a denser, smoother composite surface compared with WS-based composites. In contrast, the larger and more irregular straw particles in WS blends produced a heterogeneous surface morphology with voids and protrusions. This uneven surface likely affected the distribution and retention of the chitosan solution during application, resulting in less uniform coating coverage and greater variability in coating uptake. For the BSD blends, the average coating weight of two layers was 98 g·cm⁻². In a four-layer coating, the weight increased substantially, reaching an average of 177 g·cm⁻². In contrast, the WS blends exhibited greater variability in coating weight of two layers, with an average weight of 43 g·cm⁻². The application of four layers led to a pronounced increase in coating weight, with an average value of 133 g·cm⁻².

The WS substrate exhibited lower chitosan adhesion compared to BSD, likely due to the specific structure of the straw particles, which contain hydrophobic compounds such as waxes [32] that may hinder the adhesion of the initial coating layers. Overall, the data demonstrated an

Fig. 2. Microstructure of MBC blends in cross section: (a) BSD1; (b) BSD2; (c) BSD3; (d) BSD4. (e) WS1; (f) WS2; (g) WS3; (h) WS4. Birch sanding dust (BSD), wheat straw (WS), hemp shives (HS), birch sawdust (BS), wheat bran (WB), mycelium (M), and voids (V). Scale bar 500 µm.

Fig. 3. MBCs with chitosan surface coating: (a) BSD1; (b) BSD2; (c) BSD3; (d) BSD4. (e) WS1; (f) WS2; (g) WS3; (h) WS4. Birch sanding dust (BSD), wheat straw (WS), hemp shives (HS), birch sawdust (BS), and mycelium (M). Scale bar 2 mm.

increase in coating weight with the number of applied layers for both substrate types and indicated higher variability among WS blends compared with BSD blends.

3.3. Mechanical performance

3.3.1. Compressive properties

Substrate type significantly affected compressive strength. Both untreated and chitosan-treated BSD specimens demonstrated higher strength performance than respective blends of WS specimens (Fig. 4). The strength values ranged from 0.10 to 0.24 MPa and 0.02–0.08 MPa for untreated BSD and WS specimens, respectively. The highest compressive strength (0.24 MPa) was observed in untreated BSD1 ($\rho = 0.25 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$) composites containing sanding dust without a co-substrate. In the WS substrate group, the highest strength (0.08 MPa) was demonstrated by untreated WS3 specimens ($\rho = 0.15 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$) with sawdust co-substrate.

The highest compressive strength among chitosan-coated specimens (0.11 MPa) was achieved in the BSD1 and BSD3 blends, whereas the WS3 blend reached a maximum value of 0.06 MPa. The number of chitosan layers did not significantly influence compressive strength,

whereas substantial differences were observed across different substrates. BSD1 displayed significantly higher compressive strength than all other substrates ($p < 0.001$).

The compressive strength was more affected by the density than the chitosan coating (Fig. 4). The density of composites containing BSD ranged from 0.14 to 0.25 $\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$, whereas composites with WS exhibited lower densities, ranging from 0.10 to 0.15 $\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$. Density exhibited a strong, positive, and statistically significant correlation with compressive strength ($R = 0.920$, $p < 0.001$).

The compression modulus of elasticity (E) ranged from 1.12 to 2.40 MPa and 0.26–0.83 MPa for untreated BSD and WS specimens, respectively (Fig. 5). A strong, positive, and statistically significant correlation was observed between density and the modulus of elasticity ($R = 0.920$, $p < 0.001$). The number of chitosan layers did not have a significant effect on E values. Notable differences were observed among the various substrate blends. Specifically, substrates BSD1 and BSD4 exhibited significantly higher values than all other substrates ($p < 0.001$).

Expanded polystyrene (EPS), the primary commercial competitor of MBCs, is characterized by low density (0.012–0.048 $\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$) and compressive strength values ranging from 0.035 to 0.69 MPa [33].

Fig. 4. Density and compression strength at 10% deformation (σ_{10}) of MBCs with two-layer and four-layer chitosan coating.

Fig. 5. Density and compression modulus of elasticity (E) of MBCs with two-layer and four-layer chitosan coating.

Although EPS shows a broader strength range, untreated MBCs demonstrated competitive compressive performance, with maximum values of 0.24 MPa. This result confirmed the potential of MBCs as bio-based alternatives for low-load-bearing applications. Chitosan-coated MBCs exhibited lower compressive strength (0.11 MPa). Chitosan coating served primarily as a surface modifier rather than a structural reinforcement phase.

Because compressive strength and modulus showed a strong positive correlation with density ($R = 0.920$, $p < 0.001$), specific compressive strength and specific modulus were calculated to evaluate the structural

efficiency of the composites independent of density differences. This normalization allowed comparison of mechanical performance on a mass basis and enabled assessment of strength-to-density relationships among BSD- and WS-based blends (Fig. 6).

Analysis of specific compressive properties demonstrated that BSD-based composites exhibited significantly higher specific strength and specific modulus than WS-based blends. Increasing chitosan coating thickness significantly reduced ($p < 0.001$) both specific compressive strength and specific modulus, particularly in BSD composites, which confirms that surface functionalization did not enhance structural

Fig. 6. Specific compressive strength (a) and modulus of elasticity (b) of MBCs with two-layer and four-layer chitosan coating.

efficiency relative to density. Substrate selection, therefore, remains the primary determinant of compressive performance in MBCs.

3.3.2. Flexural properties

Substrate type had a significant impact on flexural strength. The flexural strength of the BSD composite controls ranged from 0.05 to 0.10 MPa, with higher values of BSD1 and BSD2 blends (Fig. 7). The lowest flexural strength was exhibited by the BSD4 blend with the pure sanding dust substrate. Lower strength values were observed in WS-containing composite controls, ranging from 0.03 to 0.09 MPa. In the WS substrate control group, the highest flexural strength of 0.09 MPa was achieved for the WS3 blend with a sawdust co-substrate.

For chitosan-coated MBC specimens, the highest strength of 0.13 MPa was achieved both for BSD2 and WS3 blends. Flexural strength increased significantly with an increasing number of chitosan layers. Specimens without chitosan coating exhibited significantly lower flexural strength than those with two ($p = 0.021$) or four layers ($p = 0.003$).

Densities of BSD-containing composites ranged from 0.14 to 0.23 g · cm⁻³, while WS-containing composites exhibited lower densities, ranging from 0.10 to 0.16 g · cm⁻³. A weak but statistically significant

positive correlation was found between specimen density and flexural strength ($R = 0.375$, $p < 0.001$).

Higher flexural modulus of elasticity (E_f) was demonstrated both in untreated and chitosan-treated BSD composites in comparison with the WS composites (Fig. 8). In the BSD group, the highest modulus of 4.52 MPa was achieved for the BSD4 blend, while two-layer and four-layer chitosan-coated specimens reached a maximum of 4.21 MPa (BSD3) and 3.08 MPa (BSD2), respectively. The highest modulus within the WS substrate group demonstrated WS3 blend with sawdust co-substrate, both in controls and chitosan-coated specimens (2.69 – 3.80 MPa). A moderate, statistically significant positive correlation was observed between specimen density and the modulus of elasticity ($R = 0.635$, $p < 0.001$). The number of chitosan layers did not have a significant effect on E_f values. However, significant differences in modulus were observed among the various substrate types.

The flexural strength of synthetic insulation materials such as EPS and extruded polystyrene (XPS) has been reported to be approximately 0.3 MPa [34] and 0.5–0.6 MPa [35], respectively. These values remain higher than those of both untreated and chitosan-treated MBCs. Nevertheless, chitosan functionalization increased the maximum flexural strength of MBCs from 0.10 MPa to 0.13 MPa, which demonstrates

Fig. 7. Density and maximal flexural strength (σ_{fm}) of MBCs with two-layer and four-layer chitosan coating.

Fig. 8. Density and flexural modulus of elasticity (E_f) of MBCs with two-layer and four-layer chitosan coating.

the capacity of surface modification to enhance bending performance. Importantly, unlike EPS and XPS, chitosan-coated MBCs originate from renewable resources, remain fully biodegradable, and allow production through low-energy processes, which provides significant environmental advantages.

Given the significant correlation between density and flexural properties, specific flexural strength and modulus were calculated to compare mechanical efficiency independent of the density differences (Fig. 9).

Specific flexural strength significantly increased with the addition of two and four chitosan layers ($p = 0.005$ and $p < 0.001$, respectively), reaching maximum values of $0.94 \text{ MPa} \cdot \text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$. Significant differences were also observed between substrates ($p < 0.05$). In contrast, the specific flexural modulus was higher in BSD-based composites but significantly decreased ($p = 0.007$) with increasing coating thickness. These findings indicate that chitosan surface functionalization improved strength-to-density efficiency, while stiffness efficiency remained primarily affected by substrate type.

The observed differences in mechanical performance between BSD- and WS-based composites can be attributed to variations in substrate microstructure and its interaction with the mycelial network. BSD

particles generally exhibited a finer particle size distribution and higher packing density, which promoted more uniform substrate consolidation and improved interfacial contact with the growing mycelium (Fig. 3). This enhanced the formation of a denser and more continuous mycelial matrix, resulting in improved load transfer and higher mechanical strength. In contrast, WS-based substrates consisted of more elongated and heterogeneous fibrous structures, which led to increased porosity and less efficient particle packing. Although this morphology could support fungal colonization, it may result in weaker interfacial bonding and a more open structure, thereby reducing overall mechanical performance. These microstructural differences provide a plausible explanation for the higher compressive and flexural strengths observed in BSD-based composites compared to WS-based counterparts.

3.4. Water absorption

Water absorption of MBC specimens was evaluated after 2 h and 24 h of immersion (Fig. 10). The first 2 h represented a critical period, after which the rate of water uptake decreased. Water absorption showed a clear dependence on substrate type.

Within the BSD-based group, the BSD3 blend with a sawdust co-

Fig. 9. Specific flexural strength (a) and modulus of elasticity (b) of MBCs with two-layer and four-layer chitosan coating.

Fig. 10. Water absorption of MBCs with two-layer and four-layer chitosan coating after 2 h and 24 h immersion.

substrate exhibited the lowest absorption among all BSD formulations, with values of 340–354% after 24 h. The corresponding untreated BSD3 control showed a comparable absorption of 350%, indicating that this substrate composition inherently provided improved moisture resistance. Although chitosan coating did not reduce water absorption in BSD-based composites, the treatment maintained moisture uptake at levels comparable to those of the controls and provided additional surface-functionalization benefits, including reduced wettability, improved flexural performance, and enhanced surface integrity.

For WS-based composites, the lowest water absorption was observed in the WS4 blend without co-substrates, with chitosan-coated specimens reaching 213% after 24 h of immersion (Fig. 10). An increase in the number of chitosan coating layers led to a further reduction in water uptake, and four-layer coatings exhibited significantly lower absorption than both untreated and two-layer specimens ($p = 0.001$). A reduction

of approximately 20% after 2 h and 30% after 24 h was recorded when comparing uncoated specimens with four-layer coatings. These results demonstrated that chitosan surface functionalization enhanced water resistance in WS-based mycelium composites. Since WS composites exhibited higher porosity and larger void spaces, the coating provided a more pronounced barrier effect, particularly with increasing layer number. In contrast, the denser microstructure of BSD composites may have restricted the relative contribution of surface functionalization to moisture resistance.

Reported water absorption values for wood composites (WC) typically remain below 50%, even for relatively porous systems such as particleboards (PB), while medium-density fiberboard (MDF) shows substantially lower uptake due to its higher density and the use of hydrophobic resin systems [36]. Similarly, literature data for alternative lignocellulosic PB indicate water absorption levels below 100% [37]. In

Fig. 11. Adsorption isotherms of MBCs with two-layer and four-layer chitosan coating.

contrast, the untreated MBCs examined here demonstrated high water absorption (312–655% after 24 h), attributable to their highly porous structure and the hydrophilic nature of the ingredients.

3.5. Hygroscopic sorption

The moisture content of MBC specimens increased significantly with rising relative humidity (RH) (Fig. 11). At 90% RH, untreated BSD- and WS-based composites exhibited moisture contents of 13–17%, whereas at 95% RH the values slightly exceeded 20% for all blends except BSD4 and WS4. Chitosan surface functionalization generally promoted higher moisture uptake, and greater coating thickness resulted in higher moisture contents. At 90% RH, composites coated with two chitosan layers maintained moisture contents below 20% for all blends except WS2. At 95% RH, moisture contents exceeded 20%, with a maximum value of 33% for WS2. Specimens coated with four chitosan layers exhibited significantly higher moisture contents than both uncoated controls and two-layer coatings ($p < 0.001$). The higher moisture uptake observed in chitosan-coated specimens, particularly those with four layers, could be attributed to the hydrophilic nature of chitosan. Even after ammonia treatment, chitosan retained a substantial number of hydroxyl- and amino-functional groups, which readily interacted with water molecules. Increasing coating thickness increased the number of available hydrophilic sites.

Consequently, thicker chitosan layers exhibited greater moisture sorption under high relative humidity conditions. WS-containing composites showed greater susceptibility to hygroscopic moisture uptake than BSD-based blends, particularly the WS2 formulation with a hemp co-substrate, which reached a maximum moisture content of 46% and differed significantly from the other blends ($p = 0.041$). Overall, exposure to high RH conditions (90–95%) increased the moisture content of chitosan-treated MBCs above 20%.

In MBC systems, chitosan coating improved surface protection against liquid water ingress. However, its intrinsic hydrophilicity increases vapor-driven moisture sorption under high relative humidity, particularly when applied in thicker layers. A similar behavior was observed in an earlier study [38] for pristine chitosan films, where measurable water vapor permeability attributed to the hydrophilic nature of chitosan and its affinity for water molecules was reported. The apparent difference between hygroscopic behavior and liquid water absorption of MBCs can be explained by the different moisture transport mechanisms involved. Under high relative humidity, moisture uptake is governed primarily by vapor diffusion and internal pore structure. The denser and more compact microstructure of BSD-based composites likely restricted vapor penetration, resulting in lower equilibrium moisture contents. In contrast, during immersion, liquid water absorption is driven by capillary forces and polymer swelling. The higher chitosan uptake in BSD composites increased the hydrophilic mass per unit area, which promoted swelling and contributed to greater liquid water absorption.

Moisture contents of conventional WC used in the furniture industry, such as high-density fiberboard (HDF), medium-density fiberboard (MDF), raw particleboard (rPB), and laminated particleboard (IPB), as well as building materials including three-layer plywood (3-ply), multi-functional panels (MFP), and oriented strand board (OSB), have been reported to range between 15% and 20% at 97% RH [39]. Untreated birch plywood and thermo-hydro-treated (THT) plywood exhibited slightly higher equilibrium moisture contents of 25–28% at 98% RH [40]. In comparison, both untreated and chitosan-treated MBCs demonstrated competitive moisture performance relative to these WC under high-humidity conditions. However, the present results indicate that chitosan surface functionalization may not be advantageous at extreme RH, as thicker coatings tended to increase hygroscopic moisture uptake.

3.6. Contact angle measurements

Contact angle measurements evaluated the effect of chitosan protective coating on the surface wettability of MBCs (Fig. 12). Measurements on uncoated specimens were not feasible, as water droplets absorbed immediately due to exposed cut surfaces. Chitosan coating increased contact angles, which indicated reduced wettability. BSD-containing composites exhibited higher values than WS-based composites. Specimens coated with two chitosan layers showed higher contact angles than those coated with four layers. The decrease in contact angle with increasing layer number may relate to the greater availability of chitosan functional groups and the larger effective surface area, which enhanced interactions with water molecules [41–43].

For BSD-based specimens, the contact angles of chitosan-coated surfaces decreased below 60° after 30 s. WS-based composites exhibited contact angles below 40° at 30 s, which reflected the more hydrophilic character of this substrate. Blends composed of pure substrates, BSD4 and WS4, showed lower contact angles than other MBC chitosan-coated formulations, which may relate to slower mycelial development on unmodified substrates. Fungal mycelium contains hydrophobic proteins and glycoproteins, such as hydrophobins, which can reduce the overall wettability of MBC surfaces when sufficient surface coverage occurs [44]. However, on cut specimen surfaces, wettability was governed primarily by the exposed substrate rather than by the mycelial layer. Overall, these results confirmed that chitosan modified surface wettability, with the extent of the effect dependent on coating thickness and substrate type.

Chitosan and its derivatives or copolymers, often combined with natural compounds, have been extensively investigated for paper coatings, where they improve hydrophobicity, reduce wettability, and impart antibacterial properties [45–47]. These studies have shown that chitosan forms a continuous film on the paper surface, yielding contact angles of 80 – 90° , whereas uncoated papers exhibit initial contact angles of 60 – 70° that decrease to 20 – 30° within 10 s [24,43]. In the present study, the initial contact angle of MBCs could not be measured directly due to rapid absorption. However, the observed increase in contact angle after chitosan treatment indicates that the coating effectively reduced the wettability of MB materials.

Chitosan-coated MBCs exhibited contact angles comparable to those of other porous natural fiber composites. For example, hemp-, flax-, banana-, and pineapple-fiber composites with epoxy resin have reported contact angles of 55 – 75° [48], which are lower than those observed for BSD-based MBCs in the present study. In a similar investigation of indoor OSB boards coated with epoxy/polyester, initial contact angles ranged from 60 to 70° , decreasing to 56 – 67° after 10 s [49]. In our MBC samples, contact angles declined more rapidly over time. However, the overall values remain comparable to those of these wood-based composites, indicating that MBC materials could be suitable for similar indoor applications. Similarly, the contact angle dynamics of certain BSD-based MBCs resemble those reported for MDF with a sanded finish. In MDF, initial contact angles ranged from 85 to 105° , while less polished surfaces showed a reduction to 40 – 50° within 30 s [49]. Our results for BSD-based MBCs are comparable, suggesting that these materials exhibited surface wettability behavior similar to conventional WC.

At present, the MBCs developed in this study cannot match the performance of polystyrene, which maintains contact angles above 90° for over 60 s [50], or oil-treated wood and other naturally coated surfaces, which retain contact angles above 60° over the same period [51]. These findings indicate that further research into alternative natural coatings is needed to reduce the wettability of MBCs and improve their surface hydrophobicity.

4. Conclusions

BSD-based composites, both untreated and chitosan-coated,

Fig. 12. Surface contact angles of MBCs with two-layer (2) and four-layer (4) chitosan coating.

exhibited higher compressive and flexural properties than WS-based blends. Chitosan coating did not improve compressive strength, which remained mainly affected by composite density and substrate composition. Substrate type represented the main factor affecting the compression modulus, and denser BSD blends showed higher stiffness than WS composites. Flexural strength increased significantly after chitosan treatment, whereas the flexural modulus of elasticity showed no significant change. Specific compressive properties were higher in BSD-based composites and decreased with increasing chitosan coating thickness, indicating that structural efficiency remained primarily influenced by substrate type. In contrast, specific flexural strength increased with coating thickness in both BSD and WS blends, whereas specific flexural modulus remained higher in BSD composites and showed limited improvement with coating.

Multiple chitosan layers reduced water absorption in WS-based composites by up to 30%. In contrast, WS-containing composites were more susceptible to vapor-driven moisture sorption than BSD-based blends at high RH. Vapor sorption is diffusion-controlled, whereas liquid water absorption is capillary- and swelling-driven, which explains why BSD composites showed lower hygroscopicity but higher immersion water uptake. Chitosan coating reduced surface wettability, with BSD-based composites exhibiting higher contact angles than WS-based blends. Two-layer coating provided a greater increase in contact angle, whereas additional layers reduced this effect. Substrate selection and coating thickness strongly influenced composite performance, and further optimization through coating refinement or densification may improve moisture resistance under highly humid conditions. Future work could explore refined chitosan coating strategies, hybrid coatings, or densification techniques to enhance both mechanical performance and hygroscopic stability. Additionally, long-term durability, environmental exposure, and scalability of BSD- and WS-based composites merit further investigation to enable broader practical applications.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ilze Irbe: Writing – original draft, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Mikus Kampuss:** Software, Investigation, Data curation. **Martins Andzs:** Investigation, Data curation. **Inese Filipova:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Data curation. **Laura Andze:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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